

Enhanced BIM Requirements for Quantity Take-Off: A Framework for Definition, Validation, and Application

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Abstract

This dissertation explored the improvement of BIM-based Quantity Take-Off processes in the construction industry, with a particular emphasis on the specification and validation of information requirements. It addressed the critical need for clear, standardized information specifications to facilitate accurate quantity extraction and reliable cost estimation.

To achieve this, the research developed a comprehensive framework by focusing on the definition, communication and verification of these requirements. Key outputs included the development of tools such as the Requirement Guideline API tools, which displayed requirement sheets within the Revit authoring platform, and the Coordinates Tool, which defined and validated spatial scopes within a BIM project. Additionally, the framework incorporated state-of-the-art tools like the Information Delivery Specification for automated validation and ensured compliance through systematic model checking. A case study of a Data Center

facility, provided by industry partner BIMMS, served as a proof of concept for the proposed framework. The study demonstrated the framework's ability to enhance the reliability of Quantity Take-Off processes by ensuring that BIM models in IFC format adhered to specified requirements, leading to more accurate Quantity Take-Offs, Bills of Quantities, and interactive reporting.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/11JfDIYbLnc>

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